

Ways of Integrating Digital Literacy into Foreign Language Activities (Exploratory Analysis of Convergences between the DigComp and CEFR Frameworks)

SERRAR Marwan¹, IBRAHIMI Ahmed²

^{1,2}Humanities and Education Laboratory, ERDLM, ENS Tétouan, Abdelmalek Essaadi University

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 17 February 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: SERRAR Marwan</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Language teaching ; digital literacy ; CEFR ; DigComp</p>	<p>In a context characterized by increasing digitalization, teaching in general and language teaching in particular must keep pace with these trends by integrating digital literacy alongside language skills. The aim of this integration is to help learners develop not only language skills, but also the digital competencies they need for optimal professional and social integration. However, the way in which this integration is achieved remains a subject of reflection and a major challenge. This is the logic behind this work, which aims to suggest ways of integrating digital skills into a language course, based on an exploratory analysis of the DigComp and CEFR frameworks.</p>

I. INTRODUCTION

In an digitized world, teaching in general, and foreign language teaching in particular, must evolve to meet the new challenges, needs and opportunities of the digital age. Digital literacy, as defined by the DigComp 2.2 framework (VUORIKARI et al., 2022), and language skills, as mentioned in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (Council of Europe, 2023), are two complementary areas that have the potential to enrich language learning if integrated into the same pedagogical device. According to Kern (2021), in addition to the essential skills for using ICT, the digital environment and skills have a considerable influence on language use and learning, and vice versa. Consequently, it is vital for today's language learner to also master the skills needed to interact in this environment. However, to ensure that digital skills are properly integrated alongside language skills in a foreign language course, it is necessary to carefully analyze the convergences and synergies between them. In addition, it is useful to identify the digital skills and sub-skills that can be integrated into each activity and language skill. It is with this in mind that this study aims to explore the convergences between these two types of skills, with a view to identifying potential avenues for their harmonious integration into pedagogical activities. The aim of this study is to carry out an exploratory analysis of the skills described in the DigComp and CEFR frameworks, in order to highlight possible synergies and suggest ways of integrating them into language teaching. It will thus provide a

starting point for future research and practical applications in the field of language didactics.

II. METHODOLOGY

For this study, we opted for an exploratory analysis. The aim was to find compatibilities between the digital skills and sub-skills mentioned in the DigComp framework and the CEFR language activities. The aim is to identify ways of integrating certain digital skills into the activities of a foreign language course. The digital skills chosen are those prescribed by the DigComp 2.2 framework for citizens (VUORIKARI Rina, Kluzer, & Punie, 2022): information and data literacy; communication and collaboration; safety; problem solving. With regard to the CEFR language activities targeted by the study, we will take the main activities to be : Written and oral expression, written and oral comprehension, and written, oral and online interaction.

III. RESULTS

In order to identify the compatibilities between numerical skills and language activities, we have drawn up a comparative table of these components below. It should be noted that the list of sub-skills is not exhaustive, as some are purely numerical and therefore unsuitable for a foreign language course.

Table 1: Link and synergies between digital competencies/ literacy and language activities

<i>Digital competencies/literacy</i>	<i>Dub-skills adaptable to an FLE/FFL course</i>	<i>Compatible language activities</i>	<i>Possible synergies and ways to adapt</i>
Information and data literacy	Consult, search, filter and evaluate information.	Reading comprehension	Search for texts on the Internet / analyze and evaluate the quality of sources / understand the linguistic and epistemological aspects of the text (are they facts or mere opinions?).
Communication and collaboration	Interact	Written , oral and online interaction	-Interact via digital platforms and environments / Participate and engage in discussions and chats in the target language. - Oral and written expression activities in remote mode.
	Share and publish	Oral and written production	-Share and publish videos; audio or written material according to course themes. -Publish your CV and professional content in the target language on a professional platform or social network such as LinkedIn.
	Collaborate	Oral and written interaction	-Co-writing productions -Collaborate on a class project or online group discussions.
	Respecting digital codes	The socio-cultural component of all language activities.	-Study and respect the norms of online communication in the target culture. - Include this sub-skill in the socio-cultural component of activities.
Digital content creation	Creating digital content	Oral and written production	Create multimedia content (audio, video, written) in class or online to practice the language.
Probleme solving	Find the help you need in the event of a technical problem	Oral and written comprehension	Search for, find and understand relevant information on a problem in the target language.
Safety	Protecting personal data	The socio-cultural component of all reading and listening activities.	
	Preventing spam	The socio-cultural component of all language activities.	Distinguish between real and fake news During online activities (especially on professional social networks), distinguish genuine information and people from mere spam.

IV. SYNTHESIS AND DISCUSSION :

This analysis enabled us to highlight possible synergies and areas of convergence between the digital skills of the DigComp framework and the language skills and activities of the CEFR framework for integration into foreign language courses. In what follows, we first summarize the results. Then'll look at their pedagogical implications.

A. Summary of results :

The analysis carried out on the digital skills of the DigComp framework and the language skills of the CEFR highlighted several points of convergence:

- Reading comprehension allows a number of digital skills to be integrated into a language course, including "Consulting, searching for, filtering and evaluating information" via a number of activities. These include

"Searching for texts on the Internet / analyzing and evaluating the quality of sources".

- The digital skills of interaction and collaboration are directly linked to oral and written interaction and production, fostering action-based learning practices through participation in online forums or the co-editing of documents.

- The sociocultural component of language communication skills allows us to integrate respect for digital codes, spam prevention and personal data protection into our language activities.

These convergences show that the integration of digital skills is not just limited to the correct use of new technologies and ICTE, but also contributes to working on and enriching language skills and preparing learners to become autonomous and critical users in the digital environment with the target language.

B. Discussion of pedagogical implications :

The results of this study have several implications for the design of foreign language courses. These include :

- The integration of digital skills can contribute to more engaging and interactive learning. For example, the use of forums and collaborative platforms makes it possible to create real-life exchange situations relevant to the learner's daily life. Consequently, in addition to stimulating written and oral interaction skills, this approach can also help optimize the action-oriented approach recommended by the CEFR.

- Digital content creation skills could enable learners to develop their expressions (written, oral, audiovisual) by producing multimedia projects (videos, podcasts ...). This integration has the potential to enhance learners' ability to express themselves creatively, critically and coherently, which would have a positive impact on learners' language, digital and even transversal skills.

- The integration of safety practices and respect for digital rules allows us to introduce the socio-cultural aspects of Internet use, which makes it easier to adapt these skills in a foreign language course scripted with an action-based approach. What's more, this integration is crucial to developing sociocultural skills in harmony with our modern age.

V. CONCLUSION AND PROSPECTS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The exploratory analysis carried out in this article highlights the convergence and synergy between the language skills mentioned in the CEFR and the digital skills defined by the DigComp framework. Firstly, this study shows that it is perfectly possible to teach digital skills in a foreign language course by integrating them into language activities. Secondly, this work underlines that this integration offers a significant opportunity to reinforce and enrich language activities, as well as broadening the socio-cultural component of language

skills to enable learners to practice the target language in a world that is largely based on digital technology, while being familiar with its principles and workings.

Consequently, the points of convergence identified make it possible to improve language activities by making them more interactive, more adapted and closer to our contemporary reality, which is in line with the logic of the action-oriented approach. What's more, this integration has the potential to enable teachers not only to foster the development of language skills, but also to prepare learners to become critical and autonomous users of new digital technologies with the target language.

Finally, this work opens up a number of perspectives for the improvement and expansion of foreign language teaching, including: research into the effectiveness of integrating digital skills into a foreign language course; the development of suitable didactic and pedagogical resources; the training of trainers in relation to this theme; the impact of this integration on the development of learners' skills, as well as their degrees of commitment and motivation.

REFERENCES

1. Conseil de l'Europe. (2023, 08 29). Cadre européen commun de référence pour les langues (CECR). Récupéré sur www.coe.int/fr/web/common-european-framework-reference-languages/the-action-oriented-approach.
2. Kern, R. (2021). Twenty-five years of digital literacies in CALL. *Language Learning & Technology* v25 iss3, 122-150.
3. SERRAR, M., & IBRAHIMI, A. (2024). COMMENT PRÉSERVER L'INTERACTIVITÉ DE LA COMMUNICATION PÉDAGOGIQUE DANS UNE CLASSE DE LANGUE ÉTRANGÈRE EN MODE SYNCHROME ET ASYNCHROME? (CAS DE L'USAGE DE « TEAMS » ET « ALTISSIA » DANS UNE CLASSE DE FLE). *Journal des Sciences de l'Information et de la Communication*, 1(2), 114-130.
4. VUORIKARI Rina, R., Kluzer, S., & Punie, Y. (2022). *DigComp 2.2: The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens-With new examples of knowledge, skills and attitudes*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.